

THE ROLE OF RESEARCH-BASED LEARNING TO ENHANCE RESEARCH AND ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS AND TYPES OF PROJECTS

Author: **Holikova Laylo Fakhriddinovna**,
Teacher of Samarqand State Institution of Foreign Languages.

layloholikova390@gmail.com

Abstract *The publication promotes an innovative method called project based learning and research based learning created according to the new educational standards for the teacher of Higher educational establishments and schools. This article aims to help teachers of foreign languages and students build academic content knowledge and skills, develop deeper understanding, build 21st century success skills such as research skill, writing skill, critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration creativity, innovation. It also intends to help learners become aware of their own academic, personal, social development.*

Keywords: *individual projects, short-term projects, individual projects, team projects, educational projects.*

Today, as a teacher we have so many ideas about how to develop students' research and writing skills. Students with a growing interest are always on the search of new knowledge, interested in new developments, ideas and insights. However, research skill is more than just for a class assignment. So, how to develop this competency? According to types of implementation, projects are classified into different types.

- according to the scholars research projects are subdivided into individual, team and class projects;
- according to the nature of the main learning activity: projects production, communication, organization, etc.;
- according to their more or less political or strategic dimension: educational project, foreign language learning project, educational project and training project.

Obviously, we will easily understand here that these different types of projects are neither presented in optimal order, nor mutually exclusive. Therefore, it will be less question in this chapter of a watertight typology that of perspectives different from which one can consider the nature of educational projects. So let's take the distinctions in order presented in the previous lines.

According to the temporal extent within class, projects can of course vary in the time required for their completion. Arbitrarily, we will say that the projects that are done over a period of one to two weeks are short-term projects, those that spanning a period of three to twenty weeks are rather in the medium term, while those who are practically asking the entire school year are considered to be long term.

Short-term projects

Short-term projects are certainly the easiest to manage "pedagogically both for the learner and for the teacher. They sort of correspond to what we could call "micro-projects". We must also recognize that the use of such projects in school learning did not wait for an explicit pedagogical approach like that of project-based learning gives it citizenship before exercising. All teachers who have at heart to energize and concretize their teaching strategy have, sooner or later and often, appealed to this type of projects.

This is the case when we ask students to bring to the next history lessons practical suggestions of methods or ways to use in class to better understand how our ancestors lived in Quebec. Collecting photos of family, for example, could turn out to be a happy suggestion of learners. However, a real approach per project requires time for investigation and implementation bigger to bear all its fruits. In succession, not only micro-projects can be short of breath, but they also carry the risk of lacking consistency between them and therefore to encourage learning in grains of rosary beads that convey little meaning or educational intent.

Medium-term projects

The medium-term projects appear in a way as a central link in a structured learning process and prolonged. On its own, this type of project does not generally

satisfy not all the educational intent, but it is the support main. Generally, medium-term projects are similar long-term projects, except for their duration. However, they also differ in that they set the table, so to speak, to other educational activities that will come reinforce the targeted learning. For example, a teacher of physical education could suggest to groups of students to prepare a mini-show of rhythmic dance, another of muscle strength, agility and speed of execution in a sporting activity, etc.

These mini-shows would then be used in a subsequent part of the course as a basis illustration of more formal or theoretical information on the functioning of the main muscles of the body, on the motor coordination, on reflex functions, etc. Better again, this teacher might even ask his groups of students that they suggest project ideas to facilitate the acquisition of identified knowledge. So we see here that it is a generally intermediate role that the project plays at medium term in a prolonged learning sequence and relatively substantial. The teacher who uses in his practice medium-term projects must therefore first have fairly precise idea not only of the expected product of the project and its intended goals, but also how it counts retrieve the learning achieved in the training plus scope that it must provide to learners. It's for this reason that a medium-term project should not in principle complete a school year, but rather fit into teaching structure where the distinction between the objectives specific, intermediate and teaching terminals is pedagogically well established, with the place of the project to medium well-defined term with regard to these objectives.

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Individual projects

Authors such as Bru and Not (1987) consider that it would be regrettable to abandon or neglect individual projects in the name of a group pedagogy that is starting to suffer from gluttony. According to them, such projects have their place in pedagogy and they see no contraindication to their use. On the background of the question, they are probably right. But virtue must often settle for imperfection.

First of all, it should be noted that the projects - especially those that are medium and long term - appear most of the time as substantial projects, which pursue several objectives, require a variety of skills, require knowledge various and require the execution of several different tasks. The learner alone is generally far from being a man-orchestra capable of responding to all these requests.

In this sense, projects carried out by more than one learner appear advantageous. In addition, in the context of current teacher-student ratios, we may

seriously doubt that a teacher can supervise with great attention and efficiency from 25 to 30 individual projects in a class. He could still do it in the case of short-term micro-projects, but it would probably be fast exceeded in the case of substantial projects.

There is also a risk of logistical problems in a class with individual projects: insufficient work areas, material in limited quantity, supervision or presentation time too short to meet everyone's needs, etc.

Finally, if it is true that project-based learning develops intentionally or at the margins of relationship skills interpersonal, why then do we do without? We do not give up on individual projects and we recognize quite their legitimacy. We are simply saying that their use is subject to several constraints and they turn out to be more suitable for small and short learning activities term. So much for the reserves. However, in the context of activities learning restrictions that we have just mentioned, it It is clear that individual projects also have their usefulness in pedagogy.

Not only do they ensure that the interests of all learners in a class will be considered – this which might not be the case in collective projects -, but they also ensure that each of the learners will be able to contribution some of his skills and develop others even his individual project. Therefore, the formula of the project will have, so to speak, been optimized in its claim to join each of the students in the learning to be achieved.

Team projects

In an earlier work (Proulx, 1999), we discussed in detail of the advantages and limitations of teamwork on learning and pedagogy plans. We will not resume therefore not these words here. We will say rather that in the current context of school organization, team projects are probably the most functional types of projects and the easiest to implement in a redesigned pedagogy. In at the same time as they enrich the training of learners by their diversity, they greatly reduce the sum of the requirements or particular constraints inherent in individual projects and they expose

the learner less to a certain monolithic which could result or escape from class projects.

Class projects

Class projects are projects which, in terms of content learning, are based on a common denominator to the whole class. To some extent, they focus attention learners and mobilize their energy towards the same target. For example, in a geography class, a whole class-group could be brought to establish a geographical map populations according to their race, their religion, their territory, their education, their economic condition, etc. Certainly, we can see it here, such a project can be divided into different parts of interest to small groups of learners. The fact remains, however, that the expected product is the same for all: a geographic map of the populations. We understand while a dynamic of interdependence and complementarity to be established will quickly impose itself on people involved in this project. The expected benefit maybe very obvious, but the obstacles of the course more numerous, each not working at the same pace nor with the same ease in terms of resources. Class projects ambitious deserve to be encouraged, but the danger of "putting all his eggs in one basket" is real. It is therefore necessary to this. In this regard, design projects that are sufficiently flexible and broad so that most of the content objectives of a course can benefit effectively.

According to the nature of the main activity learning as most projects have multiple objectives learning and hence call for various tasks for their realization, it becomes possible to distinguish them summarily in relation to the main learning activity they seek.

Few authors, however, have exploited this vein. In a work published in 1991, Palmade presents under this angle a classification by W.H. Kilpatrick which seems interesting to us, but that we will modify somewhat in the name of the third category of projects according to this classification.

Collaborative projects

Even if in general any project is characterized by a form of production or another, the production projects considered here are those who explicitly call for the

making of product, to a confection, literally speaking. Build scale model, make recreational furniture for improve a school park, establish a luminous sky map, make clothes or draw clothes patterns futuristic or traditional, so many examples of products which give rise to manual and technological operations which change more or less shapeless material to a more defined and more functional. These types of projects are generally very motivating for the people who work there, but they have the disadvantage of requiring a lot of material resources that the school environment is not always able to guarantee.

In consumer projects, learners use of products, works or services in place to make one benefit in terms of school learning. Set up a school cuisse in collaboration with a financial institution, set up a recycling service, organize a show circuit are all projects that fall into this category.

In these types of projects, the product in the broad sense refers more to activities held and use than in terms of learning than actual material goods. If they sometimes constitute major challenges from an organizational point of view, they are also, mutatis mutandis, less expensive in terms of material resources.

Problem solving projects

As their name suggests, the draft resolutions of problems mobilize learners' ability to solve problems for which the solution exists or not at the moment when these are posed, but without being then known to the learner. Intuition, agitation, creativity, anticipation, practical and formal reasoning are skills particularly requested by this type of project. Riddles, riddles, mind games, word puzzles, number and assembly games belong of course to this category. But we can conceive this type of projects in a much broader and more extensive way in terms of profitable learning. Submit a model efficient operation of a hospital, design a plan for research to slow down biological aging, simulate a process that would explain construction techniques

The learner who tries to meet, to its measure and within its limits, such challenges not only develop the intellectual skills mentioned previously. He prepares

without realizing too much for work itself as an agent of change and progress in the society that awaits it.

Functional learning projects

In the Kilpatrick classification presented by Palmade (1991), it is referred to as "technical improvement projects" to report on this type of project. The expression "Functional learning" seemed to us to be more adequate in terms of what this category includes projects that bring learning to master a certain number of technical operations, theoretical or practical from data or objects existing.

Mastery of software, conditioning of animals, learning a language or communication codes, driving a motorized vehicle, learning clockwork mechanisms, musical instruments, rules parliamentarians, etc., these are all examples of so-called functional learning. Sometimes entire courses constitute alone such projects. Language courses, driving automotive, rescue, etc., are examples. But, generally, in the school context, these projects fit into learning objectives and content wider. For example, we will take advantage of a biology course animal to learn within a project how birds build their nests by making one yourself. This type of projects, of course, is characterized by its great flexibility. of use in pedagogy. So it's no wonder that we use it frequently, especially when we want to illustrate theoretical data or when we want to bring the learner, by an inductive process, to discover for himself certain theoretical laws or properties that apply to an object learning.

According to their political or strategic dimension recent years have seen the emergence of educational circles and in the terminology they use a "flight of types of projects" whose various names are confusing more than the layman.

Educational projects, training, educational projects and establishment projects are among the expressions most used to qualify certain types of projects with more or less institutional scope.

Although these types of projects are not new to the most of it is gargled over and over again today in the jargon educative. Let's try to see things clearly, even if,

strictly speaking, these types of projects are rather on the periphery of learning projects.

Educational projects; in accordance with the words of Joannert and Vander Borgh (1999) on this subject, we will say of educational projects that they are projects developed mainly by a group or a team of teachers who share a common situation teaching and who decide to work together in it around a common pedagogical model. This type of projects is certainly the one that best suits the project-based approach. This, in fact, can precisely result, as an educational formula, an educational project having favored this approach. Usually projects teaching are prepared and tested by team's teachers working within the same class group or the same program in a school. For example, a group of sixth grade teachers' year in an intensive English program might decide teaching.

For reasons of better synergy, comparability and equity, it is desirable that projects are mainly developed and carried out by teachers working with students from the same class group or who follow the same program. Of course, we should not exclude that an educational project can be carried out by the entire teaching staff in a school, but the marked differences between levels and programs in the same establishment easily suggest that an educational project planned, for example, for first-year learners of the secondary will not necessarily bear the same fruits for fifth secondary learners.

Training projects

Unlike educational projects which, in principle, were only set up by a team of teachers, the training projects are projects developed by various agents of education, which range from the teachers themselves to the staff executive through representatives of the community and the people to train themselves. Of course, learners most of them have their own training project, but so understood here, the training project has a larger and refers to the decisions made by educational environment to offer a program in a given environment qualifying course, after a well-defined reading of the social needs expressed in the community. In this sense, such projects first find their justification in their report with the political or strategic

situation from which they originate. Strictly speaking, they have little to do with educational formulas themselves.

Educational projects

Educational projects are generally projects that involve all the staff of a school around mainly certain values to be promoted in all relationships experienced at school. When, for example, an establishment decides to respect, autonomy and a sense of responsibility three fundamental values conveyed and embodied within its walls, we will say that his educational project is made up of these elements essential. Obviously, such a project is not limited to putting some key values in the foreground; he sets out principles and beliefs; he prescribes behavioral standards desired or prohibited; it favors operating modes or activity, etc. We can think here that, depending on the very content of the educational project, the educational formulas may vary although this is not always the case. If, for example, the staff of a school wanted to favor openness to others and cooperation at work in leisure or other activities, teamwork could then constitute an educational formula which would fit well into such an educational project.

Establishment projects

Among the types of projects mentioned above, establishment projects are certainly those whose dimension «Political" is the most obvious. These projects always cover an official character in that they are the subject of decisions taken by the higher authority in a school, i.e. the board institution or the board of directors. Of course, such projects have, in the course of development and implementation, ramifications at different levels of the institution, but first of all the bodies mentioned above which adopt it and which follow up. Another characteristic aspect of projects establishment is that they cast a very broad cast on subjects likely to hold their attention. It therefore does not concern necessarily the teaching itself. For example, a tip establishment could have plans to expand its school park, to redesign and repaint the interior of school, to set up a cafeteria service for students, etc.

All these projects would certainly constitute establishment projects, but their impact would be very indirect on education as such. In this, these projects can

appropriately work according to the will and priorities of the staff approved by the governing body, whether or not it has a tangible effect on pedagogy practiced at school. It is clear, for example, that a tipoff an institution that would decide to invest, massively in the purchase of computer equipment for teaching purposes would at the same time create a shock wave spread over the practices educational programs in force within its walls.

In general, it is also desirable that it be so, that is to say that the establishment projects focus as much as possible on what is at the heart of the institutions' mission.

We will not go any further in examining type projects political or strategic, which affect less directly the educational intervention in itself.

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